

INVESTIGATION OF PEOPLE'S MORAL ATTITUDE WHO CAME TO THE SPORTS CENTER

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study is to examine moral attitude differences of the people who come to sports centers in terms of some variables. In this study, Moral Attitude Scale, which is developed by Prof. Dr. Mevlüt Kaya, is implemented to 190 people who are from different sports centers in Burdur city center. In statistical analysis (frequency analysis) of the obtained data from the individuals who regularly do exercise (150 people) and do not regularly exercise (40 people), independent t test and one way ANOVA analysis were used. It is observed that the individuals who came to sports center regularly have higher moral attitude scores compared to those who do not come regularly. As a result, it is observed that there is no statistical differentiation in moral attitude evaluations between the people who came to sports centers in terms of demographic variables such as age, gender, income status.

Keywords: sports centers, morals, attitude

1. Introduction

The concept of moral maturity expresses the total of the most necessary and richest moral characteristics which is suitable to the state of being the best in terms of emotions, thoughts, decisions, attitudes and behaviors. Moral maturity is the highest level which provides individual to feel every immorality in his/her feelings, thoughts, decisions, attitudes and behaviors in his/her conscience. An individual who have reached moral maturity, is a good human who is trustworthy, responsible, respectful, fair, can control himself/herself, developed empathy skills (Kaya and Aydın, 2011).

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According to Fukuyama (1998), moral maturity requires to absorb moral values and place moral values in person's conscience. In order to have moral maturity it does not enough to just carry moral values as emotion, thought and judgement. Also, those values must be turn into attitude and behavior conscious becoming moral habit of all of these reveal moral maturity (Kaya and Aydın 2011).

With the study called "Investigation of People's Moral Attitude who Came to the Sports Center" a study is aimed on determining moral attitude differences of the people who came to Burdur city's sports centers and regularly do exercise and the ones who come but do not regularly exercise.

Today, there are researches about the effects of participation to sports on moral attitudes. However, it is observed that there limited number of studies especially about investigating the moral attitude differences between sports' participants. This research in this context has been seen as an important work because it will primarily provide source to the relevant literature. In addition, research findings are important to investigate while it is necessary to make sports regularly, to continue to gyms, to have a planned life, and alongside these, it will give other researchers, who are about to conduct study on this field, a prevision.

Dictionary meaning of sports is all of the body movements applied according to some rules, made in the form of individual or collective competitions. According to Büker's definition of sport in 1993; *"It is an aesthetic, technical, physics, contestant, and social process for peaceful form of play, distraction and departure from work, depending on the increase in free time of basic skills and fighting methods that people gain when fighting nature"* (Büker, 1993).

According to Schönholzer (1985), it means an English word "Fit" -We cannot find it exact German and French translation- "appropriate", "eligible" and at the same time "suitable", "beneficial", "capable" and "ready". Actually, the word is translated as "being in a good form" and "being at a higher level" at the second level.

According to Schönholzer (1985), the parts involved in the body belong to the fields of medicine, anthropology and exercise physiology. But what is the meaning of "health" here? If, according to the official definition of the World Health Organization, it really includes the state of spiritual and social well-being, we are already accepting absence of physical and mental disease or infirmity as general and strong tendency.

According to Schönholzer (1985), with time, there are changes happened in the field of thought in Greek era. While being professional athlete is met exuberantly, it started fall into contempt gradually. Increasing physicalness hostility became more visible in Late Antique Age. In Christian Europe, this thought continued. However, West Medieval was more moderate than the ages of Rococo and Baroque. Later, Age of Enlightenment gives importance to physicalness with a regressing tendency like in existentialism.

According to Schönholzer (1985), there is no need to go that back to search fitness history. With Industrial Revolution, training styles and methods were developed and the people who are involved with ports are gradually increased. After this period, the living conditions of the people have changed in very large scale and instead of the

population of people engaged in livestock and agriculture mainly in countryside, the number of people living with much less physical activity and doing repetitive work has risen considerably. Depending on these conditions, many diseases have increased in human population. Such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases.

According to Schönholzer (1985), together with the understanding of people doing exercise in their free times and try to be fit is a must for health, it is revealed the truth that sports is not just a luxury or a waste interest. All of these developments, starting from the middle 1900s, lead the flow of healthy life and fitness which are about to have their current form especially in 70s and 80s.

According to Alpers and Segel (2009), Joseph Pilates is the leader of the fitness movement in America and the creator of the Pilates method which he called "Contrology" (Alpers and Segel 2009). According to the statements in Everything Pilates Book of Alpers and Segel's (2009), the movement capability of human body fascinated Joseph Pilates. Evelyn Ringold, in her piece which is published in New York Herald Tribune, wrote that she studied Pilates' anatomy books and quoted one thing; *"I read all the pages about the body parts and move every part that I have learned."* Pilates said this when he was eighty-six; *"I am right, because I did not take even one aspirin. For all of my life I never felt sick even for one day. If all people do my exercises they will definitely be happier"*.

According to Alpers and Segel (2009), Joseph Pilates went to his homeland Germany and is known in there and also attracted German government's attention. When German government ask Pilates that train new German army, Joe thought that this changing political environment will put in danger his progress on his path, he take the road to Amerika.

According to Yapan (2007), the word morals is plural version of the word "hulk" which means habit in Arabic. When looking at the origin of the word, it is seen that Morals covers the character, attitude, behavior and habit that a human has. Morals can be considered as rules, limitations and evaluations which order humans' attitudes and behaviors (Quoted by: Çoymak, 2015).

According to Baysaling's (2000) definition of morals, it is a system of rules which are referenced with the aim of regulating human behaviors and human relationships and used on judging other humans' behaviors in positive and negative way. And according to Durusoy (1991), these are generally are not written and this is the aspects of them that differs them from legal order; but morals and law are the rules that society obey and identify with each other from time to time. According to Öngel (1997), humans must obey moral rules because, morals offer humans virtues to regulate their behaviors (Quoted by: Çoymak, 2015).

It is a truth that in daily life, the actions which are determined and acted by humans have sometimes good, sometime bad results. The concept of morals aims humans to reach mature pleasure feeling spiritually and both develop and reveal his/her spiritual characteristics and abilities. The concept of morals aims best life style for humans (Quoted by: Çoymak, 2015).

According to Atilla Erdemli (2006), sports are a game based on movement. Like in every other game, sports have natural rules and principles which it gained with

being a game. Even if they change according to each sports branch, there are fundamental rules and principles in sports phenomenon in whole. There are embodies sports as a moral case.

According to the statements in Sports Morals and Problems book of Şahin (2018), sports activity is started to become a social phenomenon which is realized with participation to various sports branches by today's organized-unorganized individuals from every age level. In the light of science and technique, while the people, whose working hours are decreasing, constitutes middle level of the sports pyramid, students who are mandatorily drifting to two training with increasing population constitutes the bases of this pyramid. It is seen that, in the top of the pyramid, there are the ones that choose sports as profession.

According to Öngel (1997), from the beginning of humanity's history, it was always in humans' mind to affect sportive success from outside, unrightly. Alongside this, the existence of the thought that act sportsmanlike and gentlemanlike is old as humanity history.

Lumpkin in the year 1990 explained the concept of ethics, as *"In the concept of ethics, there is sensitiveness to individual needs and differences, responsibility for personal behavior, attention to other people, integrity and commitment to Fair-Play."* (Quoted by Mirzeoğlu et al. 2006). And according to Orhun (1991), when we look at the ethical values in sports, the concept of Fair-Play, it covers high and universal values of human's. The last step of being a human is human to reach high values (Quoted by: Öngel 1997).

Lumpkin et al. (2003) stated that, whatever the athlete's religious belief is, sports' and its morals' values are universal and ethical rules are involves these. Lumpkin et al. (2003) summarized them with the titles of people's values, principles, beliefs, moral and social values in society and emphasized that these values are very important on development and life of both society and people.

When related sources are studied, it is seen that there are many definitions about attitudes. The most known of this is according to smith (1968) attitude is "tendency which is laid to an individual and creates his/her thoughts, emotions and behaviors about a psychological object (Quoted by: Murat and Uygun, 2004). Kağıtçıbaşı (1988) stated that attitude is not a behavior which can be seen, it a tendency which preparer for behavior (Quoted by: Canakay, 2006).

According to Canakay (2006), when looking at all of these definitions, we conclude that attitudes can change and can be changed. According to this, negative attitude can turn into positive and positive attitude can turn into negative. When considering attitudes are the basis of thought and behaviors, it is seen that it is necessary to develop positive attitude while directing an individual to success. As known, sports is an important activity field with its contribution of the aspects both individual and social health, and morals.

2. Method

In this research, descriptive survey model which aims exact description of existing truth was used. Survey model is “an approach with the aim of descript a past or current situation with its existing form” (Karasar, 2012). Researcher gave information about the research to participants, and they have been told that complete volunteering is fundamental. Researcher, in the implementation phase of the research, have active role on conducting the study in healthy way with making necessary explanations to people who come sport centers in filling surveys.

For study, three sports centers are determined in Burdur city center which is serving for Fitness. These sports centers are University Sports and Health Center, Olimpia and Oxygen. 140 people who regularly do exercise, 50 people who do not regularly exercise are filled the moral attitude scale face-to-face.

In research, as data collection tool, “Moral Maturity Scale” which is developed by Kaya and Şengün (2008) was used. Moral Maturity Scale is a Likert type scale, which consists of 66 items and 5 levels, and aims to measure the moral maturity levels of the individuals. It is strengthened with 10 demographic questions to measure people’s demographic characteristics. Kaya and Şengün (2008) previously found the reliability co-efficient of test - re-test as 0,88, the reliability co-efficient of test - half test as 0,89 and the reliability co-efficient of Cronbach Alpha as 0,93 of the scale.

For the obtained data analysis SPSS 15.0 package program was used.

3. Findings

The descriptive statistical information related to the obtained findings from data collection tool which is performed in the scope of research are presented in the tables below.

Table 3.1: Percentage Distribution of Participants’ Groups

Group	f	%
Regularly do exercise	140	73,7
Do not regularly exercise	50	26,3
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.1, it is determined that 73,7% of the participants are regularly doing exercise and 26,3% of them are not regularly doing exercise.

Table 3.2: Percentage Distribution of Participants’ Age Group

Age groups	f	%
20-30	137	72,1
31-45	46	24,3
46 or older	7	3,7
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.2, it is determined that 72,1% of the participants are in between 20-30 age group, 24,3% of them are in between 31-45 age group, and 3,7% of them are 46 or older.

Table 3.3: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Gender

Gender groups	f	%
Female	76	40
Male	114	60
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.3, it is determined that 60% of the participants are male and 40% of them are female.

Table 3.4: Percentage Distribution of how many years that Participants Regularly Doing Exercise

Duration	f	%
1-12 months	87	44,9
1-4 years	44	13,5
5 years and more	59	31,5
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.4, it is determined that 44,9% of the participants are regularly doing exercise for 1-12 months, 13,5% of them are for 1-4 years, 31,5% of them are for 5 years and more.

Table 3.5: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Birth Places

Birth Place	f	%
City Center	119	62,6
District-Town-Village	71	37,4
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.5, it is determined that 62,6% of the participant were born in city center, 37,4% of them were born in district-village-town.

Table 3.6: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Educational Status

Educational Status	f	%
High school	39	20,5
College (2 years)- College 4 years	51	79,4
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.6, it is determined that 20,5% of the participants are high school graduates, 79,4% of them are 2 years college and 4 years college graduates.

Table 3.7: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Graduated Faculty or College

Faculty or college	f	%
Faculty of Education	61	32,1
Faculties of Veterinary-Science-Literature		
Faculties of Economics-Engineering	52	27,1
Vocational school	12	6,3
Other, please state	77	40,5
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.7, it is determined that 40,5% of the participants are graduated from different faculties or colleges, 32,1% of them are graduated from faculty of education, 27,1% of them are graduated from faculties of economics, arts and sciences, engineering, veterinary and 6,3% of them are graduated from vocational schools.

Table 3.8: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Occupational Status

Occupational group	f	%
Student	111	58,4
Worker	16	8,4
Artisan	6	3,2
Officer	37	19,5
Other, please state	20	10,5
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.8, it is determined that 58,4% of the participants are students, 19,5% of them are officers, 8,4% of them are workers, 3,2% of them are artisans and 10,5% of them are in different occupational groups.

Table 3.9: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Marital Status

Marital Status	f	%
Married	46	24,2
Single	144	75,8
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.9, it is determined that 75,8% of them are single and 24,2% of them are married.

Table 3.10: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Monthly Average Income

Income status	f	%
300-900 TL	92	48,4
901-1500 TL	32	16,8
1501-2100 TL	16	8,4
2101 or above	50	26,3
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.10, it is determined that 48,4% of the participants' monthly income are 300-900 TL, 26,3% of their monthly income are 2101 and above, 16,8% of their monthly income are 901-1500 TL and 8,4% of their monthly income are 1501-2100 TL.

Table 3.11: Percentage Distribution of Participants' Doing Exercise Status How Many Times a Week

Duration of doing exercise	f	%
1-2 days a week	40	21,2
3-4 days a week	124	65,2
5-6 days a week	20	10,5
7-8 days a week	5	2,6
Other, please state	1	,5
Total	190	100,0

According to Table 3.11, it is determined that 65,2% of the participants are doing exercise 3-4 days a week, 21,2% of them are doing exercise 1-2 days a week, 10,5% of them are doing exercise 5-6 days a week, 2,6% of them are doing exercise 7-8 days a week and 0,5% of them are doing exercise for different durations.

Table 3.12: Comparison of Participants' Moral Attitude Points

Group	N	X	Ss	F	p
Regularly do exercise	50	118,62	27,382	,084	,772
Do not regularly exercise	140	120,24	30,016		
Total	190	238,86	57,398		

According to Table 3.12, it is determined that the participants' who regularly do exercise moral attitude points are $118,62 \pm 27,382$ and the participants' who do not regularly exercise moral attitude points are $120,24 \pm 30,016$. According to the obtained findings, it is determined that there is no statistically significant difference between the moral attitude point of the participants who regularly do exercise and those who do not ($p > 0.05$).

It can be thought in the basis of there is no significant difference between moral maturity attitudes of the participants who regularly do exercise and those who do not, because the participants in both groups have exercising habits. However, it can be defended even if the participants who do not regularly exercise have lower exercising habits compared to those who regularly do exercise this result is obtained due to both of these groups have exercising habits and also have sportive personalities.

4. Results and Recommendations

It is determined in the research individuals' who regularly do exercise moral attitude points show significant difference according to their gender ($p < 0.05$). According to this, male participants who regularly do exercise have higher moral attitude points than females. While 52 female participants' moral attitude points determined as 110, 27, 88 male participants' moral attitude points determined as 123,21.

When regularly doing exercise situations of the research participants' moral attitude points are evaluated, it is determined that the averages of moral attitude points are $261,02 \pm 47,340$ in 1-12 months of doing exercise, $241,54 \pm 70,960$ in 1-4 years of doing exercise, $234,27 \pm 47,018$ in 5 years and more of doing exercise. According to obtained

findings, it is determined that the averages of moral attitude points of the individuals in research show significant difference according to their duration of doing exercise ($p < 0.05$).

According to obtained findings, it can be say that duration of regularly doing exercise is determinant on moral attitude. Compared to other participants, participant who are doing 1-12 months and 1-4 years of regular exercise have high moral attitude point shows that doing regular exercise has positive effect on moral attitude. However, it can be defended in the basis of participants who are doing exercise 5 and more years have lower moral attitude point compared to others is because duration of their weekly or monthly exercise and their perception about exercise and frequency of participation to exercise is low compared to individuals who are started exercising newly. In the researches in the literature, it is determined that regularly participating sports contributes development of moral characteristics. According to Woods (2011), participation to sports and physical activity gives people chance to develop themselves in the matters such as truth, integrity, responsibility and modesty and also offers people moral dilemmas that they have to solve. And Lee, Whitehead and Ntoumanis (2007) stated that sports have positive effects on moral decision-making ability (Quoted by; Gürpınar, 2014).

When educational status or their occupational status of the research participants' moral attitude points are evaluated, it is determined that the averages of moral attitude points are $125,23 \pm 25,843$ in students, $110,06 \pm 22,445$ in workers, $121,67 \pm 8,501$ in artisans, $115,51 \pm 28,408$ in officers and $113,15 \pm 37,211$ in other occupational groups. According to the obtained findings, students have the highest moral attitude point, however there is no significant difference between the moral attitude point of the participants in terms of their occupational status ($p > 0.05$).

When weekly exercising status of the research participants' moral attitude points are evaluated, it is determined that the averages of moral attitude points are $120,50 \pm 34,150$ with duration of 1-2 weeks, $119,88 \pm 24,442$ with duration of 3-4 weeks, $129,29 \pm 31,829$ with duration of 5-6 weeks, $109,25 \pm 15,327$ with duration of 7-8 weeks. According to the obtained findings, participants who exercise with duration of 5-6 weeks have the highest moral attitude point, however there is no significant difference between the moral attitude point of the participants in terms of their weekly exercising status ($p > 0.05$). It can be said that the occurring of this result is due to participants have a habit of regularly doing exercise even if they do it on different frequencies.

It can be thought that it is an expected situation that the frequency of individuals to exercise is not an important determinant on moral attitude. Nevertheless, it is necessary to encourage individuals to actively participate in sports.

The suggestions about regularly going to sports centers without health problem should be made by trainers, who are working in sports centers, according to education, age and income variables. Sports center is a center of socializing, relaxing and alongside these a center of becoming healthy. That is why, the implementations on directing people to sports centers should be made by trainers.

Socio-economic, marital and educational status of the people who came to sports center are different, however, sports centers have an important function on bringing people together. Sports centers, which are important in terms of individuals to develop friendships and values like moral, should be generalize by the people who are related with sports.

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